

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORICAL THINKING OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON TEACHING EXAMPLES OF FOLKLORE

Bekchanova Feruza Rustam kizi

Urgench innovative university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11118424>

Abstract: This article describes the theoretical foundations and importance of forming reading skills in elementary school students based on folk poetry. Opinions about getting children interested in reading are also given

Key words: Folk art, reading, education, library, fairy tale, story, mature generation.

Introduction.

Education of young people has always been considered the most urgent problem. The development of society depends on people's consciousness, intelligence, morals in many ways. A well-educated person thinks first of all about the interests of the country and the people. Because the happiness of each person is different and cannot be realized in its own way. When the people around are happy and prosperous, everyone feels happy. This rule has existed since ancient times, and it has been followed in different ways in different periods. Ideologies, ideas, political and social laws have differed from each other in different societies that mankind has experienced. Education and upbringing works served to meet the needs of the existing society as a social order. At the same time, various educational systems were formed. New views, provisions, theory and examples of practical experience have appeared. At a time when mankind did not yet know how to read and write, the views on providing education to young people were reflected in the examples of folk oral creativity. It has been tested and refined by experience for a long time. It has reached the level of strong educational influence. Even after the emergence of reading and writing, folk oral creativity did not lose its status, on the contrary, its effectiveness increased even more, being absorbed into the content of written literature.

At the stage of primary education, the study of "*The world around us*" and "*Pedagogy*" is aimed at achieving such goals as the formation of skills such as description, analysis, generalization, justification. As a result of studying this subject, the student learns about the history of the Motherland (*pictures of people's life, work, traditions of different historical periods*), the history of the motherland - the Motherland (*people's work, specific features of the profession, important historical information*). lum acquires knowledge of historical evidence. In the process of mastering these subjects, schoolchildren should be able to describe separately studied events from the history of the Motherland, show state borders, population areas, etc. on a map, globe.

The issue of formation of historical consciousness in elementary school students has been a concern of teachers and methodologists for many years. This was related to the specific characteristics of historical material acquisition and historical evidence by young students. In this regard, in the works presented by stylists in the pre-independence period, to determine the ways of enriching the historical imagination of students through the use of

figurative teaching of history in primary grades, the teacher's story, conversation, and visual teaching tools. necessity is justified.

Primary education is a stage that strengthens a child's mental education, is carried out in an integral connection with other areas of education, expands the scope of knowledge and worldview, and most importantly, ensures successful education in higher classes. Because of this, all subjects taught in primary grades, their sections, each topic and concepts are selected with special attention. Materials that ensure the growth of the student's mind in accordance with the level and level of knowledge, are used in daily life practice, and represent the essence of events and incidents that happened in life. For this, the topics included in the content of each subject are selected separately by experts and scientists. In this process, as we said above, examples of folk art are also of special importance. Folk pedagogy is the science of examples of folklore aimed at educating and training young people. The sum of educational experiences and knowledge accumulated by the mass of people in the process of marriage represents the content of the people's pedagogue. Folk pedagogy is the views of the hardworking people and wise people on the goals and tasks of education in raising young people to become well-rounded people in accordance with the expected goals, and the methods, tools, skills and competencies used by the masses of the people to implement educational work, experiences is a collection of knowledge and information collected on the basis of Using them in the educational process makes a great contribution to students' understanding of their national identity and becoming worthy children of independent Uzbekistan. Because of this, samples of folk art are included in the content of the subjects taught in primary classes.

Folk epics, proverbs, proverbs, riddles, wise sayings, legends and narratives shape the worldview of young people and create noble human qualities. Through them, the child learns about the past, labor activities, dreams and aspirations of his people. Samples of folklore make students interested in learning, create an opportunity for conscious and active learning. Samples of folklore reflect concepts that have been tested in experience for centuries, have been repeatedly used in life, and have undoubtedly yielded good results. These concepts are refined by people's intelligence and creative thinking, and are brought to a level where they acquire high artistic value. Uzbek folklore includes various types of examples, from short, well-meaning proverbs to extensive, interconnected epics. In all of these, human maturity, intelligence, strength, morals, labor activity and skills are interpreted. There are examples of folk art that can be studied at each stage of education, corresponding to different periods of the child's development, choosing them correctly, using a variety of methods and methods, tools and forms. Teaching increases the effectiveness of teaching.

There is no doubt that the examples of folk oral creativity will give positive results in the spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the current situation where the provision of national education to primary school students has been strengthened, and changes are being made to the content of education and upbringing. Loyalty to universal values, which are the foundations of the development path of independent Uzbekistan, strengthening and developing the spiritual heritage of our people, patriotism and national education, examples of folk art serve as the most effective tool. The scientists of our republic have regularly studied examples of folklore and the problem of teaching them to young people. In the studies of *H.Zarifov, I.Afzalov, M.Alaviya, M.Murodov, G'Jahongirov, T.Mirzaev, M.Obidova, Z.Husainova*, various genres, emergence and development of examples of folk art are theoretical based on

aspects. Proverbs, fairy tales and narratives, songs can be included in the types of folk art that can have a strong educational impact on students in primary grades. Riddles are analyzed more as a means of intellectual education and learning. But their educational influence cannot be denied.

Examples of Uzbek folk oral creativity, which include various aspects of life, promote high human ideals in the masterpieces of folk wisdom, which call people to morality, patience, honesty and piety, correctness and honesty is made. The language and artistic features of fairy tales, riddles, and proverbs, which are studied more often in primary grades, are distinguished by their interrelated and different aspects. While other genres of folklore are mainly intended to implement various directions of morality and education, riddles have mostly been a means of influencing the intellectual maturity of young people. Riddles are somewhat close to problem-based learning. A problem question, a task, an assignment, even some riddles can create a problem situation for the student. Since this idea will be analyzed in more detail in the next chapters, we did not dwell on it.

Conclusion.

To sum up, the spiritual and moral formation of primary school students takes place under the influence of the school, family and society. This direction of the child's development determines what kind of person, specialist, person and society he will be necessary and useful in the future. Nothing can be overlooked in the education of elementary school students. There should be no "small", "insignificant", "trivial" things in child education. It is always necessary to remember that "big" problems arise from these trivial things. It was found that even if the samples of folk art are used outside of school, when the child is tired of TV and computer, it is possible to make a great contribution to mental, moral and health.

References:

1. Sh. Mirziyoyev "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people" T: Uzbekistan, 2017;
2. Newly revised State Education Standard on Primary Education Primary Education. Tashkent, 2005. - No. 5, pages 5, 6, 8-9.
3. Newly revised curriculum for primary education Primary education. Tashkent, 2005.
4. The concept of primary education Primary education, 1998, No. 6.
5. Unified State Education Standard and Curriculum. Tashkent, 2010.
6. Yangibayeva, N., & Yusupova, M. (2022). The concept of perception and thinking in psychology. its principles. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 2(11), 50-53.
7. Qizi, Y. N. S., Saboxon, O., Risolat, A., & Salomat, S. (2022). Oral teaching methods in primary school nature classes. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 2(11), 88-90.
8. Shernafasova, H., & Yangibayeva, N. (2022). Pedagogical problems of improving the educational process in preschool educational organizations. Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика, 1(19), 31-34.

